

Building ORCID Communities of Practice in Pakistan

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Overview

This project (**Building ORCID Communities of Practice in Pakistan**) fosters equitable ORCID adoption in underrepresented research communities, including HEIs, R&D organizations, and regional institutions. Through needs assessments, bilingual training, outreach, and a sustainable ORCID advocates network, the initiative targets a 25% adoption increase, trains 200 individuals, forms 100 advocates, and enhances global collaboration. It builds capacity, strengthens infrastructure, and promotes open research in Pakistan.

How widely and deeply will this project benefit the focus communities

1

The project will deeply focus Research communities in Pakistan, a lower-middle-income country, by targeting underserved HEIs, R&D organizations, and regional institutions with limited ORCID awareness.

2

This project will build ORCID Community of Practice through bilingual training, workshops, and online resources tailored to the needs of researchers, administrators, and librarians.

3

By training 200 individuals and establishing a network of 100 ORCID advocates, This project will foster sustained ORCID adoption, empowering researchers to connect globally.

4

This project will impact over 10,000 individuals as trained advocates disseminate knowledge and integrate ORCID into institutional workflows.

Project objective

1. **Raise Awareness of ORCID Benefits**
2. **Building ORCID Community of Practice in Pakistan**
3. **Fostering Sustainability in ORCID Community of Practice**
4. **Promoting ORCID initiatives in the region while Enhancing Global Collaboration**

ORCID Adoptions Trends

Global Adoption Trends

Overall Adoption: Recent studies indicate that ORCID adoption among academic researchers has reached approximately 72%, with variations across disciplines and demographics.

The adoption rates differ by field, ranging from 17% in the visual and performing arts to 93% in biological and biomedical sciences.

ORCID Adoptions Trends

Global Adoption Trends

Countries like the UK, Finland, Portugal, Australia, Austria, and Czech have high adoption rates (80–90%), often due to national funder mandates requiring ORCID iDs in grant applications.

ORCID Adoptions Trends

Adoptions Trends in Global South & Pakistan

ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) adoption varies across regions, with the Global South, including countries in Africa, Latin America, and South Asia, generally exhibiting lower adoption rates compared to more developed regions.

In Pakistan, ORCID adoption remains particularly limited. A study focusing on Pakistani scholars revealed that only about 5,020 researchers had registered for ORCID IDs, highlighting a low level of awareness and engagement with the platform.

Why this project?

The "Building ORCID Community of Practice in Pakistan" project addresses the need for equitable access to ORCID iDs in underrepresented research communities in Pakistan. Targeting HEIs and R&D organizations, it aims to enhance global visibility and collaboration for Pakistani researchers. Through a needs assessment, bilingual training, and building an ORCID Advocates Network, this project will overcome adoption barriers and integrate ORCID into research workflows. The initiative aligns with global open science goals, contributing to a more inclusive research ecosystem and positioning Pakistani researchers for international recognition (the main moto of this project besides promoting ORCID initiatives).

How is the project structured?

For Building ORCID Community of Practice in Pakistan project is structured into phases

Needs Assessment (Month 1-2):

- Conducting surveys and focus groups to identify barriers to ORCID adoption.
- Engaging stakeholders, including researchers, librarians, administrators, and policymakers.

Training Material Development (Month 2-3):

- Creating bilingual (English and Urdu) training resources, including:
 1. Training modules on ORCID integration and best practices & 2. Outreach materials such as guides, infographics, and case studies

Capacity Building Workshops & Trainings (Month 4-6):

- Organizing in-person workshops in major cities (Karachi, Lahore, Islamabad, Peshawar, Quetta).
- Delivering virtual webinars for researchers in remote areas.

Activities & Solutions

Establishing of ORCID Communities of Practice (Month 6-8)

- Creating the ORCID Pakistan Network, a collaborative group of ORCID advocates.

Outreach Activities (Month 6-9):

- Training 100 ORCID advocates to promote adoption.
- Hosting events, including conferences and [Open Research Days](#), to share experiences and best practices.
- Develop localized resources and organize events.

Monitoring & Reporting (Month 9-12):

- Track adoption, evaluate, and report outcomes. The project ensures success through continuous monitoring, collaboration, and adaptation.

Target audience

The target audience to establish ORCID community of practice in Pakistan includes:

- 01 | Scientific Editors of Journals
- 02 | University's Professors
- 03 | Researchers from Universities and HEI's
- 04 | PhD Scholars
- 05 | Researchers at R & D Organizations

Deliverables

Increased ORCID Adoption

25%

Adoption by Pakistan's leading higher education institutions (HEIs) and research organizations.

Enhanced Institutional Capacity

200

Train at least 200 researchers, administrators, and librarians on ORCID integration.

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Deliverables

Establishing ORCID Community of Practice

100

Building a network of ORCID advocates to mentor peers and sustain adoption efforts.

Global Integration

100%

Facilitating connections between Pakistani researchers and the international ORCID ecosystem.

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Risk Management and Mitigation

- 01 | **Risk:** Low participation from HEIs and researchers.
Mitigation: Partner with the Higher Education Commission (HEC) and leading universities to drive engagement.
- 02 | **Risk:** Challenges in sustaining momentum post-project.
Mitigation: Train ORCID advocates and integrate ORCID adoption into institutional frameworks for long-term sustainability.

Sustainability and Scalability

The project's sustainability will be ensured by:

Developing reusable and accessible training materials for all stakeholders

100%

Establishing the ORCID Pakistan Network to provide ongoing support

100%

Encouraging institutional policy changes to embed ORCID into regular workflows.

100%

Scalability will be built into the project's framework, enabling expansion to other South Asian countries with similar challenges

Vision

Promote Open Access

We advocate for open licensing and digitization of cultural assets and scholarly content ensuring that everyone can explore and use these treasures.

Foster Collaboration

We bring together cultural institutions, academic institutions, scholars, artists, and technologists to innovate and create new ways to engage with openness in cultural heritage and science.

Empower Education

We provide resources and tools for educators, students, and lifelong learners to harness the power of cultural heritage and open science in their studies and projects.

Team

The core team of XploreOpen includes:

1. Dr. Muhammad Imtiaz Subhani
Founders of XploreOpen.
2. Amber Osman,
Co-founders of XploreOpen.
3. Imran Sheikh
Sr. Tech Advisor

Founder of XploreOpen

Dr. Muhammad Imtiaz Subhani

Dr. Subhani, with a PhD in Financial Econometrics and a Postdoc in Open Science, is a passionate advocate for open science and ethical initiatives in scholarly communication. Dr. Subhani is an award-winning journal editor (earned Web of Science Scholar One vision award in 2015). He currently holds a position of Professor & Director of Post Graduate Studies & ORIC at ILMA University. He serves as a DOAJ Ambassador & Editor, a Crossref Ambassador, and a Director of FORCE11, focusing on promoting open access publishing, best practices, and liaising with key stakeholders. He's a lead of Creative Commons Pakistan, a policy expert on Open Science at UNESCO and an IP specialist at World Bank. He's also an Editor of PLOS ONE, a scientific publishing consultant for the Higher Education Commission, Govt. of Pakistan, and an author of numerous scientific articles.

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Co-Founder of XploreOpen

Amber Osman

Amber Osman is a passionate expert in open science and a research enthusiast. Over the last decade, she has been actively involved in different international academic, research & publishing organizations and with the Higher Education Commission (Govt. of Pakistan). She has been an award-winning journal editor for advancing the publishing process by adopting innovative research and publishing solutions. Amber advocates for best practices in open access scholarly content.

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Thank you.

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